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Deliverable D2.1

D2.1 The DocEnhance curriculum

(for integration of transferable skills in PhD programmes)

17/06/2022

SUMMARY

This report summarizes the body of knowledge for doctoral programs in each of the major disciplines and highlights their commonalities and differences focusing on transferable and soft skills important for the further career of graduates in academia, in private (commercial/business) sector, nonprofit organizations and public institutions. The main goal is an effective integration of transferable skills in PhD programmes and the high quality of the offered courses based on a modular concept. To create this report, we have examined curriculum guidelines for doctoral education and have referred to the transferable and soft skills and other supporting information as necessary. Furthermore, we used the experience obtained during the development and pilot implementation of three transferable skills courses based on the concept of three consecutive modules (online, group work, and non-academic experience). College-level faculty and administrators of doctoral schools and/or doctoral study programs are the audiences for this report.

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INTRODUCTION

The DocEnhance curriculum aims to respond to the current problematics of doctoral studies and create a plan for modern high-quality doctoral education. The outcome of this research is to tailor curriculum recommendations to the rapidly changing landscape of required skills both within and beyond academia, to improve the employability of PhD graduates and to ensure their outstanding competencies for their future careers in the global (at least European) environment. Even though the Deliverable No. 1.2 (What comes after a PhD? Findings from the DocEnhance survey of doctorate holders on their employment situation, skills match, and the value of the doctorate) summarized that “doctorate holders reported good levels of satisfaction with most aspects of their doctorate programmes, although satisfaction with the support offered by programmes for pursuing academic and non-academic careers could be improved”.

Another focus of this report was on the further qualification of PhD candidates in the doctoral program. PhD holders are not only employed in the academic sector but also in the private, industrial, non-profit and public sectors, too. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare them to be capable and responsible professionals, scientists, researchers, engineers, group leaders and/or managers. The modern global world will continue to present challenging career opportunities, and those who work in certain fields will have a crucial role in shaping the future. Somewhat modified types of transferable skills are needed for different sectors of graduates' employment. The soft skills training should be compatible with the professional training in individual study programs. Hence, we comment here on somewhat general concepts of successful integration of transferable skills in PhD programmes. International sharing of experience and good practice is crucial for the further effective development of transferable skills training of PhD candidates.

For this purpose, methodological recommendations for the administrators of doctoral education (including doctoral schools), university/faculty management and other bodies involved in the further development of PhD education (including national levels and European dimensions) were developed and described in order to increase the quality of (i) European doctoral training, (ii) various doctoral study programs at the level of universities, and (iii) the tailored supervision of the individual doctoral students. Its goal is to provide perspective mainly for those in academia who need to understand what the major required disciplines/competencies are and how to use gained skills in their later work.

RECOMMENDED CURRICULUM

1.1 General comments and recommendations

Doctoral candidates may benefit mainly from getting deeply involved in research/creative projects. However, the question arises concerning to what extent their own research (independent academic/creative work) experience and academic expertise are valuable and applicable to real-world usage, i.e. to their future career mainly outside the academia. Hence, the integration of acquiring transferable skills by PhD candidates is one of the challenges for further improvements in doctoral training.

Based on current observation, the share of research work is about 60% to 90% of the workload in the doctoral study program (60% are nowadays recommended by the Czech ministry of education). For the future career of PhD graduates, different skills are needed, thus the research projects should not exceed 75% of PhD candidates' workload. However, the majority of PhD candidates are involved in academic research projects. PhD candidates/students (around the world) are under a great deal of pressure (e.g. <https://www.voxweb.nl/english/workload-on-phd-students-is-a-many-headed-monster>); “nearly one in 20 PhD students in Nijmegen drop out within the first 18 months, according to the figures Vox requested from Radboud University. A much larger proportion do obtain their PhDs, but almost never within four years – the timeframe usually given for a course of study. Only 6.5% complete their PhDs within four years (not including students at the UMC – university medical centre). 57% are finished after six years. More than a third do not receive their PhDs within two years of completing their projects.” Similarly in Czechia, the majority of PhD candidates graduated lately after more than 5 years from the date of their enrolment (based on annual reports of Czech public universities). 33–70% of those who start their PhD never finish. Some studies show that one-third of a sample of doctoral students who were still enrolled had at some point intended to drop out. In addition, of those who reach the finish line, the majority do so in (substantially) more time than initially planned (E. van Rooij, M. Fokkens-Bruinsma & E. Jansen 2021). „Poor supervision, teaching duties, publication pressure, stress over temporary appointments – these are just some of the issues that PhD students/candidates face“ (<https://www.voxweb.nl/english/workload-on-phd-students-is-a-many-headed-monster>).

Moreover, „of every ten young researchers who start PhDs, approximately eight want to continue in academia, while only one or two will ultimately get a permanent position“. The preparation for a non-academic career is enormously necessary for the majority of PhD candidates. The doctoral schools or similar concepts can help PhD candidates to obtain proper training, a guidance plan, and courses they can take for their professional development. Of course, the support in obtaining academic skills, such as research techniques and academic writing, but also support in the development of process-related skills, such as planning and management, leadership and critical thinking should be provided. Non-existent, little, or poor academic support is related to dissatisfaction, longer completion times, and even dropout

(<https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037X.2019.1652158>). The daily support of PhD candidates from supervisors is needed. Hence, the supervisors should be not only highly qualified professionals but also persons trained in supervision.

Thus, at least ca. 25% of the PhD education/formation workload should focus on various flexible forms of training and education including specialized courses & soft-/transferable skills subjects, which are nowadays in high demand. (Ca. 76% of career-tracking survey respondents (Deliverable No. 1.2 – DD1.2) indicated the offer of transferable skills training during their doctorates. Nevertheless, for 24% of respondents, there were no training transferable skills offered at their university.) Hence, as the Deliverable No. 1.2 (DD1.2) demonstrated that “most doctoral programmes offer transferable skills training, although these tend to focus on academic skills”. Entrepreneurship and Intellectual Property related skills were by far the least acquired by the responded graduates. Doctorate holders who had received transferable skills training reported statistically significantly greater competence in the majority of skills important for employability upon completion of their course than those who had not received such training. Collaboration with external organizations and stays abroad further improved some of the competencies.

As a result, subjects and training can combine practical exercises (including non-academic expertise and some type of intersectoral/international mobility) with theoretical content and concepts that should be implemented into doctoral study programs, especially in the case of transferable skills training. Furthermore, as (DD1.2) suggested transferable skills training should be promoted by supervisors. Hence, the pieces of training supervisors are important for the successful education of doctoral graduates.

Other recommendation put emphasis on experts in the field, who helps the doctoral students to focus on deepening skills that are sought-after within both the academic and non-academic (private and public) sectors. Different routes of training and courses have to be offered including self-education, group collaboration, international and intersectoral mobility and excursions/practices to properly selected non-academic institutions.

Doctoral-level education should consist of the following: research work (dissertation thesis), core subjects, interdisciplinary courses and mainly professional summer/winter schools, mobility programs and various modular/flexible forms of soft-/transferable skills training. All the components of doctoral education should be balanced, properly promoted and communicated with both doctoral candidates and supervisors. The individual doctoral plan should be tailored for every PhD candidate.

1.2 Hybrid forms of education and their benefits to students

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 introduced new techniques and approaches in the education/training process. The winners of the pandemic were those who could adapt to the online regime as quickly and effectively as possible. Students and PhD candidates had to learn from their homes and lectures and/or other types of courses started being dominantly online. In some cases, also hybrid forms of teaching were introduced. Not only PhD candidates but also their supervisors and teachers had to be adapted to new forms of education and communication. Although planned originally different, the pandemic conditions change the forms of the first piloting of the three DocEnhance courses, i.e. *Data Stewardship*, *Supervision*, and *Career Management and Entrepreneurship*, in 2021. Not only Module 1, but all the three designed modules run for the first piloting in the virtual environment without physical contact with the teachers/trainers and participants. Modules 2 and 3 were performed mainly in person or hybrid form in the second loop of piloting. The combination of the generally planned online individually performed course in Module 1, where a participant can gain a (partial) certificate, subsequent group work (in-person event, or hybrid form, or even in the virtual environment) in Module 2 and cooperation with a non-academic/business/public service entity in Module 3, proved that this course strategy should be utilized in many other professional courses as well. Based on the first piloting loop, both pros and cons can be summarized in comparison with the second piloting loop mainly performed in personal/hybrid form.

1.3 Online modules of courses

The identified general advantages of the online parts of each of the three DocEnhance courses (*Data Stewardship*, *Supervision*, and *Career Management and Entrepreneurship*) are:

- Time flexibility
- Possibility to return to the online (in the cloud, on the shared platform) saved lectures and materials and learn from them
- Lowering of staff (lecturers) workload
- Possibility to address a broader audience
- Possibility to offer easily a course outside of an institution (the online modules can be shared among universities – internationally, intersectoral assignment is possible)

The disadvantages of the online part are (if it is not combined with other modules delivered in other forms):

- Too individualistic
- Limited possibilities for teamwork
- Weaker interaction with lecturers or fellow students

Generally, the advantages of online or hybrid courses are the possibility to access the course from anywhere. Participants can be for various reasons at home or in a different country and still they do not miss a class. Furthermore, they can rewatch the recorded class or return to the saved materials. Another very significant aspect is the perfect time flexibility and individual optimization of the time spent by learning to fulfil the goals. If a course is open for a particular (quite long) period, students can sign up for it when it is suitable for them (in their day/week schedule). This also aims to address several other participants and the course becomes open to a wider audience than it would have if it took place (in a classroom/lecture hall) at the university. Such time flexibility is also very important for the training of supervisors (the target group for the developed and piloted course on Supervision). The Supervision course proved to be very significant for the eventual success rate and well being of doctoral candidates. We can speak about a secondary effect, because the course is beneficial not only for the main target group – supervisors but subsequently also for doctoral candidates of the particular trained supervisor.

For example, one of the biggest advantages of the Data Stewardship course was the month access to Module 1, where participants were allowed to watch videos, follow the study materials and make assignments. There was no time pressure and it could have been accessed from various places including home. After successfully finishing this Module 1, participants automatically received an online certificate. The second significant advantage was an easy meeting of lecturers from abroad who, thanks to the online version of the course, were able to present their views and ideas.

On the other hand, there were also a few disadvantages mainly typical for online modules and generally for the virtual learning environment. Because of the online/virtual (digital) form, some of the participants did not interact with others and just passively listened to the lecturers. Based on the lecturer's feedback, some of the students were not engaged as much as the lecturer expected them to be. The completely online form/virtual electronic environment cannot fully substitute a present form of class and all the lecturers and students agreed strongly on having some of the course modules in person (at least in the next cycle).

1.4 Group work modules

Group work is a significant means of communication and collaboration among course participants. Again, this provides a vital step of how to cooperate successfully in the team as well as the division of tasks to achieve (as a team) the maximal effectiveness. PhD candidates have to use what they had learned before (in Module 1), through practical assignments while working in small groups with other colleagues. Generally, working in a group is in many ways beneficial both for the academic and non-academic environment. The importance of teamwork and the use of teams and collaboration expectations have been consistently rising to achieve the proposed outcomes and to fulfil all the goals.

Based on the DocEnhance courses the advantages of working in groups were:

- Better and faster problem solving
- Increased potential for innovation
- Students from various fields of studies –interdisciplinary cooperation
- Personal growth
- Boosted productivity and effectiveness among students
- Intensive course in a short period

The disadvantages of working in groups were:

- Due to the intensive nature, it cannot be too long... 2 days would be optimal?
- Students need to set aside time to dedicate to the group-work
- Some teams can divide labour unequally
- Undesired type of competition within the workplace

The workload in Module 2 (group work) should be properly planned, the size of the group should be adjusted to fit the content of the course, and the teams should be supervised during their work. The groups should mix the students considering their different intersectoral/international origins, and their results in Module 1 to prevent internally homogeneous groups. Some public speaking/oral presentations of the results of the workgroups should be included as an important point of PhD training for defence of obtained problem solutions.

1.5 Private/non-academic sector involvement

The private (non-academic) sector being integrated into the majority of courses (not only in the case of transferable skills, but also for professionally oriented courses) offers practical assignments/tasks in cooperation with some business or public service entity, which helps doctoral candidates to prepare properly for a career outside academia, or even in the case of an academic career to be able to cooperate with the non-academic sector. The DocEnhance courses proved in the concept of the modules including especially Module 3 that this type of hands-on training in research represents for doctoral candidates the key experience for their future careers. Putting into practice the theoretical and practical skills acquired in the previous modules in a non-academic setting helped the participants to understand such complexity they meet in their future careers. Nevertheless, also this part had both advantages and disadvantages which should be discussed and further considered for other course development and doctoral candidates' training (mainly for acquiring transferable skills).

Based on the DocEnhance courses the advantages of the non-academic sector module were:

- New, highly attractive experience for the majority of participants
- Intersectoral skills acquired

- Teambuilding during excursion/non-academic practice
- Intensive course/training in a short period
- Transparent comparison of academic and non-academic environment

The disadvantages and issues of the non-academic sector module were:

- A time-consuming module including travel time to companies
- IP protection in some companies – only model data and/or part of data are communicated
- The selection of instructors from the industrial environment
- The selection of companies (sector, size, national/international)
- Sometimes relatively hard interconnection with the previous modules 1 and 2
- Proper selection of non-academic partners related to the topic of the course and reflecting the level of expertise of the course participants

The private/non-academic sector was represented in the piloted modules and students got this valuable experience. The DocEnhance courses proved that a part like this should be incorporated into both specialized and soft skills courses for PhD candidates. Such modules are crucial to fill the gap between academic and non-academic sectors. On the other hand, it is important to take into account if this part cannot be in some cases replaced by Summer/Winter Schools (where professionals from the non-academic sector can be present). The non/academic partners have to be detailly informed about the content of previous modules.

2 DocEnhance practice

Being part of the DocEnhance project, the UCT, Prague found good practice in the Data Stewardship course, the course that introduced students to the complexity and significance of data management. The good practice was found there mostly because data stewardship is a skill required, both within and beyond academia, as research data becomes more openly available and their usage is increasing in the existing broad variety of disciplines. Furthermore, proper data collection, data processing, data management and targeted use of data are crucial for rational and effective control in industrial companies. PhD candidates should also undertake, for instance, the study of data management with high attention to how to put into practice their theoretical and practical skills. All of the primary videos from Module 1 were available to study from the faculty Moodle system and/or DocEnhance platform. The remaining modules walked students through all the steps of research data management, from finding relevant data to managing them, publishing their own datasets, data sharing and data use for process control.

In participants' feedback, it was mentioned many times that the idea of having a course that is combined with online learning, group teamwork, intersectoral/international mobility, and academic and private/non-academic sector meeting/excursion/practice proved to be effective.

Therefore, it has to be recommended that a concept of the modular structure of similar (mainly transferable skills) courses - including different properly selected forms of education (virtual/online environment, individual self-education, group work with mobilities, intersectoral and interdisciplinary approach, practical non-academic training – ideally in mixed groups) is beneficial to fulfil the goals of doctoral education. Hence, this concept should be integrated and used as a common approach in doctoral study programs. Novel courses created using this concept should become a useful integral part of a future model for doctoral study programs.

CONCLUSION

As the PhD education continues to evolve, and new transferable and soft skills-related disciplines emerge, existing curriculum reports should be further updated. An innovative concept of three interlinking modules (i) online lectures, (ii) interdisciplinary local group work and (iii) regional assignments within the non-academic sector was successfully used for Data Stewardship, Career Management and Entrepreneurship, and Supervision. This concept will be recommended as the basis for the development of further training of PhD candidates in other transferable skills adapted at individual university levels considering the multiple competencies approach and the successful employability of PhD graduates. Furthermore, we recommend the concept of combining individual online courses (containing videos, texts, electronic exercises, quizzes and interactive content) with group work including public speaking, intersectoral/international mobility and practical education (training, excursion etc.) in the non-academic institution or at/least with non-academic experts. The workload of PhD candidates should be well balanced to minimize the stress during PhD education and prepare the graduates for both academic and (prevailing) non-academic careers. The PhD study program should somewhat reduce the research project workload and offer modular courses. The policy of universities/doctoral schools should include cooperation with the non-academic sector, especially for the preparation and performance of transferable skills training of PhD candidates.

International collaboration during the preparation of the transferable skills courses/training is highly recommended to harmonize the PhD curricula at least among cooperating universities.

Continuous development/improvement of the courses is essential reflecting the feedback from course participants, teachers, and non/academic partners.

The certificate or other form of approval has to be issued for individual modules and the whole course. Based on the university policy, credits and/or other forms of recognition should be assigned to participants to be motivated to enrol on the courses and complete them.

REFERENCES

1. Deliverable No. 1.2 (What comes after a PhD? Findings from the DocEnhance survey of doctorate holders on their employment situation, skills match, and the value of the doctorate
2. E. van Rooij, M. Fokkens-Bruinsma & E. Jansen (2021) Factors that influence PhD candidates' success: the importance of PhD project characteristics, *Studies in Continuing Education*, 43:1, 48-67, DOI: [10.1080/0158037X.2019.1652158](https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037X.2019.1652158)
3. <https://www.voxweb.nl/english/workload-on-phd-students-is-a-many-headed-monster>
4. <https://www.msmt.cz/vzdelavani/vysoke-skolstvi/vyrocní-zpravy-o-cinnosti-vysokých-skol?lang=1>
(The Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MEYS, MŠMT in Czech – annual reports of Czech public universities)
5. <https://eua-cde.org/>
6. https://eua.eu/downloads/publications/web2_council%20on%20doctoral%20education_layout_vertical.pdf
7. <https://eua-cde.org/reports-publications.html>